

ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

**Bozorbekov Ahmadjon,
Chinberdiyeva Mohlaroy****Andijan State Foreign Languages Institute**
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Abstract: This article gives information about “English as a second language”.

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Introduction

English as a second or foreign language is the use of English by speakers with different native languages. Language education for people learning English may be known as English as a second language (ESL), English as a foreign language (EFL), English as an additional language (EAL), English as a New Language (ENL), or English for speakers of other languages (ESOL). The aspect in which ESL is taught is referred to as teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL), teaching English as a second language (TESL) or teaching English to speakers of other languages (TESOL). Technically, TEFL refers to English language teaching in a country where English is not the official language, TESL refers to teaching English to non-native English speakers in a native English-speaking country and TESOL covers both. In practice, however, each of these terms tends to be used more generically across the full field. TEFL is more widely used in the UK and TESL or TESOL in the US.

Language teaching practice often assumes that most of the difficulties that learners face in the study of English are the consequence of the degree to which their native language differs from English (a contrastive analysis approach). A native speaker of Chinese, for example, may face many more difficulties than a native speaker of German, because German is more closely related to English than Chinese. This may be true for anyone of any mother tongue (also called the first language, normally abbreviated L1) setting out to learn any other language (called a target language, second language or L2). See also second-language acquisition (SLA) for mixed evidence from linguistic research

English as a Second Language (ESL) Podcast is a web-based English language-learning podcast. It is the first and longest-running English language learning podcast on the Internet. It was launched in July 2005 by two former university professors, Dr. Jeff McQuillan and Dr. Lucy Tse of the Center for Educational Development in Los Angeles, California. ESL Podcast produces four main services: free audio lessons, supplementary Learning Guides, a blog on American culture and English learning, and specialty courses

The purpose of English as a Second Language Podcast is to teach English by using everyday phrases and expressions spoken at a slow rate of speech, followed by explanations of what these expressions mean and how to use them. Learners access the lessons for free on the website or via a piece of podcast/RSS feed software such as iTunes. English is a West Germanic language that originated in England and is now the most widely spoken language in the world. It is the official language of over 50 countries, including the United States, Canada, Australia, and the United Kingdom. English is also the most commonly used language in international business, science, and technology. As a mother tongue, English is spoken by over 360 million people worldwide, making it the third most spoken language after Mandarin Chinese and Spanish. In the United States, English is the most commonly spoken language,

with over 230 million speakers. In the United Kingdom, English is the official language and is spoken by over 60 million people. English has a complex grammar system, with a variety of tenses, verb forms, and sentence structures. It also has a large vocabulary, with over 170,000 words in current use and many more obsolete or archaic words. English is known for its flexibility and adaptability, with new words and phrases constantly being added to the language. One of the unique features of English as a mother tongue is its regional variations. English is spoken differently in different parts of the world, with variations in pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar. For example, American English and British English have many differences in spelling, pronunciation, and vocabulary, and there are also many regional dialects within these varieties.

Overall, English as a mother tongue is a widely spoken and influential language that has had a significant impact on global communication, culture, and commerce. Its complexity and adaptability make it a fascinating language to study and use.

English as a Second Language (ESL or TESL) is a traditional term for the use or study of the English language by non-native speakers in an English-speaking environment (it is also known as English for speakers of other languages.) That environment may be a country in which English is the mother tongue (e.g., Australia, the U.S.) or one in which English has an established role (e.g., India, Nigeria). Also known as English for speakers of other languages. English as a Second Language also refers to specialized approaches to language teaching designed for those whose primary language is not English.

English as a Second Language corresponds roughly to the Outer Circle described by linguist Braj Kachru in "Standards, Codification and Sociolinguistic Realism: The English Language in the Outer Circle" (1985).

"Basically, we can divide up countries according to whether they have English as a native language, English as a second language, or English as a foreign language. The first category is self-explanatory. The difference between English as a foreign language and English as a second language is that in the latter instance only, English has actual assigned communicative status within the country. All told, there is a total of 75 territories where English has a special place in society. [Braj] Kachru has divided the English-speaking countries of the world into three broad types, which he symbolizes by placing them in three concentric rings:

The inner circle: these countries are the traditional bases of English, where it is the primary language, that is Great Britain and Ireland, the United States, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand.

The outer or extended circle: these countries represent the earlier spread of English in non-native contexts, where the language is part of the country's leading institutions, where it plays a second-language role in a multilingual society. e.g. Singapore, India, Malawi, and 50 other territories.

The expanding circle: this includes countries that represent the importance of English as an international language though they have no history of colonization and English has no special administrative status in these countries, e.g. China, Japan, Poland and a growing number of other states. This is English as a foreign language. It is clear that the expanding circle is the one that is most sensitive to the global status of English. It is here that English is used primarily as an international language, especially in the business, scientific, legal, political and academic communities."

"The terms (T)EFL, (T)ESL and TESOL ['Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages'] emerged after the Second World War, and in Britain no distinction was seriously made between ESL and EFL, both being subsumed under ELT ('English Language Teaching'), until well into the 1960s. As regards ESL in particular, the term has been applied to two types of teaching that overlap but are essentially distinct: ESL in the home country of the learner (mainly a UK concept and concern) and ESL for immigrants to ENL countries (mainly a US concept and concern)."

"The term 'English as Second Language' (ESL) has traditionally referred to students who come to school speaking languages other than English at home. The term in many cases is incorrect, because some who come to school have English as their third, fourth, fifth, and so on, language. Some individuals and groups have opted for the term 'Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages' (TESOL) to represent better the underlying language realities. In some jurisdictions, the term 'English as an Additional Language (<https://www.thoughtco.com/english-as-an-additional-language-eal-1690600>)' (EAL) is used. The term 'English Language Learner' (ELL) has gained acceptance, primarily in the United States. The difficulty with the term 'ELL' is that in most classrooms, everyone, regardless of their linguistic backgrounds, is learning English.

ESL stands for English as a Second Language and is used to describe non-native speakers of the English language. If you are learning English in the United States, Australia, Canada or other English-speaking countries, the term could apply to you. If you are learning English in a country where English is not common, then the phrase English as a Foreign Language (EFL) would apply. Whatever your native language happens to be, you can add English as another language skill. Whether you are in high school, college, evening classes, adult education departments, adult basic education programs, or something else, you can benefit from ESL classes and ESL courses. If you've been looking to improve your writing skills, have better translations frequency, deliver effective conversation skills with others, and more, we have online programs designed to help you. We have beginner to advanced level ESL classes to improve your proficiency levels in English.

Conclusion

Learning English as a second language can open up the door to new job opportunities. Being an ESL teacher can allow you to work in different countries teach speakers of other languages English. Using your new communication skills, you can help students in public schools, community colleges, and in graduate programs help advance their knowledge through ESL teaching. Another benefit of being an ESL teacher is that you can have the ability to travel and explore new cultures. English is in high demand in a lot of countries, so teaching English as a second language can allow you to travel to new places you've never been before.

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